

A General Synthesis of α -Unsaturated Acids from Malonic Acid. Part II.*

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Malonic acid has previously been condensed with aliphatic and aromatic aldehydes in presence of glacial acetic acid or acetic anhydride with formation of alkylidene or arylidene malonic acids by various workers such as Stuart (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1883, 43, 403; 1886, 49, 357), Kommenos (*Annalen*, 1883, 218, 145) and Einhorn and Gehrenbeck (*Annalen*, 1889, 263, 374). Riedel (*Annalen*, 1908, 361, 89) was the first to use pyridine as the condensing agent instead of acetic acid or anhydride, and instead of getting alkylidene or arylidene malonic acids, he obtained the corresponding derivatives of crotonic or cinnamic acid with loss of carbon dioxide.

In 1925, Dutt (*loc. cit.*) showed that malonic acid condensed very easily with aliphatic and aromatic aldehydes in presence of small quantities of pyridine and piperidine. It was also found that the reaction took place in presence of pyridine alone, but the addition of small quantities of piperidine greatly accelerated the reaction, producing α -unsaturated monocarboxylic acids in excellent yields in most of the cases, with rapid loss of carbon dioxide. A large number of aliphatic and aromatic aldehydes were condensed in this way and the corresponding α -unsaturated monocarboxylic acids obtained.

On account of the interesting nature of the reaction, it was thought advisable by the present authors to study it in detail and also from the quantitative point of view. Consequently a systematic procedure was adopted. In course of these investigations it was found that the reaction was essentially a catalytic one, as without the presence of a condensing agent an aldehyde of the type of benzaldehyde condensed with malonic acid with only partial formation of benzylidene malonic acid. Not even the slightest trace of carbon dioxide was evolved. It was also found that the quantity of the catalyst had a decided influence on the vigour of the reaction and the

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consequent yield of the reaction product, the best case being arrived at when the catalyst was present in the ratio of one molecule to one molecule of malonic acid. Deficiency and excess of the catalyst both seemed to diminish the yield, the former by bringing about a weak reaction and the latter by producing undesirable by-products. It was also found that *meta* and *para* compounds condensed with malonic acid giving much better yields than *ortho* compounds.

Organic bases of widely varying type have been used in bringing about condensation between malonic acid and aldehydes. As a matter of fact it has been found that practically every kind of secondary and tertiary base (primary bases cannot be used as they themselves condense with aldehydes with formation of anhydro bases) can be used in this reaction as a catalytic agent. Some of the tertiary bases used in course of this investigation (*e.g.*, dimethylaniline, diethylaniline, methylbenzylaniline, ethylbenzylaniline and quinaldine) formed simultaneous by-products (colour bases, etc.) along with cinnamic acid when benzaldehyde was used as one of the constituents of the reaction. Nevertheless, the formation of α -unsaturated acid took place inspite of the formation of large quantities of by-products.

In course of this investigation it has also been found that it is not absolutely essential to add the catalyst in the form of the free base to the reaction mixture. It can also be added in inorganic or organic acid combination. When it is in the form of an organic acid salt, the reaction takes place in the same way as if it were in the form of a free base, but when added in the form of an inorganic acid salt, the reaction is some what retarded and a higher temperature becomes necessary for the completion of the reaction (*vide* Table IV).

This investigation with widely varying types of bases was carried out in order to determine whether there was a base which could condense malonic acid with an aldehyde to a quantitative yield of the reaction product. This expectation has been realised in actual practice. The best yield was obtained in the case of lutidine which came to the theoretical. In the cases of other pyridine derivatives the yield varied between 76 and 99 per cent., whereas quinaline and its derivatives gave yields varying between 60 and 93.7 per cent. But on the other hand acridine gave only 12.2 per cent. In the case of quinaldine and 9-methylacridine the yield was abnormally reduced (23.8 per cent. and 1.5 per cent. respectively) on account of the formation of large quantities of yellow by-products (colouring matters).

Although it may be said in general that the stronger the basic character of a base, the greater is the yield of the unsaturated acid obtained by using it as a condensing agent, yet the exceptions are so numerous that such a conclusion cannot be taken with any degree of rigidity.

The following secondary and tertiary bases have been used as catalytic agents with success in the condensation of benzaldehyde with malonic acid: quinoline, isoquinoline, quinaldine, α -naphthoquinoline, β -naphthoquinoline, phenanthroline, acridine, 9-methylacridine, pyridine, α -picoline, lutidine, collidine, piperidine, dimethylaniline, diethylaniline, methylbenzylaniline and ethylbenzylaniline.

The following aliphatic and aromatic aldehydes have been condensed with malonic acid under optimum conditions using quinoline as the condensing agent: benzaldehyde, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde, *m*-, and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, vanillin, *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, *p*-tolualdehyde, veratraldehyde, piperonal, anisaldehyde, furfural, citral, citronellal, cinnamaldehyde, paraldehyde, propaldehyde, isobutyraldehyde and iso-valeraldehyde.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of Benzaldehyde with Malonic Acid in presence of Quinoline.

Ten different flasks fitted with air condensers and each containing benzaldehyde (6 g) and malonic acid (6 g.) were treated with quinoline as follows: first flask 1 c.c., second flask 2 c.c. and so on. The flasks were then put in a large water-bath and its temperature raised slowly. At about 50°, the contents of the flasks which had already solidified melted slowly and the evolution of carbon dioxide was noticeable at about 60°. The temperature of the water-bath was maintained at 80-85° and each flask was taken out of the bath as soon as the evolution of carbon dioxide was complete. The contents of the flasks were treated individually with dilute hydrochloric acid and then submitted to steam distillation in order to remove any unchanged benzaldehyde. The residual cinnamic acid which crystallised out on cooling was filtered off, washed with cold water, dried and weighed. The mother liquor also was treated to recover more of the product. The results are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I.

Quinoline added.	Duration of heating at 80°.	Yield in g.	Yield (%).	Quinoline added.	Duration of heating at 80°.	Yield in g.	Yield (%).
1 c.c.	10 hr.	4.6	54.8	6 c.c.	6 hr.	6.0	71.4
2	9	4.97	59.2	7	6	5.67	67.5
3	9	6.17	73.4	8	6	5.55	66.07
4	9	6.7	80.0	9	5	5.32	63.3
5	6	6.1	72.7	10	5	4.54	54.0

Condensation of o-Nitrobenzaldehyde with Malonic Acid in presence of Quinoline.

o-Nitrobenzaldehyde (4.5 g.) and malonic acid (3 g.) were condensed together in presence of quinoline in a manner similar to the above. The results are summarised in Table II.

TABLE II.

Quinoline added.	Duration of heating at 80°.	Yield in g.	Yield (%).	Quinoline added.	Duration of heating at 80°.	Yield in g.	Yield (%).
1 c.c.	10 hr.	2.16	38.1	6 c.c.	6 hr.	.975	17.3
2	9	2.52	44.4	7	6	.96	16.9
3	9	2.18	38.4	8	6	.96	16.9
4	9	1.57	27.7	9	5	.96	16.9
5	6	1.32	23.28	10	5	.86	15.17

The condensations of malonic acid with other aldehydes were carried on in similar manner using the most suitable quantities of quinoline (1 mol. of the aldehyde to 1 mol. of quinoline) in order to get the best possible yield. The results are summarised in Table III.

TABLE III.

Name of the aldehyde condensed.	Product.	Time taken for the reaction to complete.	Yield (%).
Benzaldehyde	Cinnamic acid	7 hr.	80.0
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	<i>o</i> -Nitrocinnamic acid	9	44.4
<i>m</i> -Nitro- „	<i>m</i> -Nitro „ „	3	82.5
<i>p</i> -Nitro- „	<i>p</i> -Nitro- „ „	3	75.0
<i>o</i> -Chloro- „	<i>o</i> -Chloro- „ „	8	71.1
<i>p</i> -Hydroxy- „	<i>p</i> -Hydroxy- „ „	10	10.6
<i>m</i> -Hydroxy- „	<i>m</i> -Hydroxy- „ „	10	70.0
Vanillin	Ferulic „	8	50.3
<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino-benzaldehyde	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino-cinnamic acid	6	68.8
<i>p</i> -Tolualdehyde	<i>p</i> Methylcinnamic acid	1	69.9
Anisaldehyde	<i>p</i> -Methoxy- „ „	5	72.3
Veratraldehyde	Dimethylcaffeic „	4	69.5
Piperonal	Piperonalacrylic „	1	60.9
Furfurol	Furfuracrylic „	4½	66.4
Citronellal	Citronellal-acrylic „	8	37.8
Citral	Citralidenemalonic „	5	74.2
Cinnamaldehyde	Cinnamylidene- „ „	5	76.5
Paraldehyde	Crotonic acid	8	40.5
Propionaldehyde	Ethylacrylic acid	12	76.8
<i>iso</i> Butyraldehyde	<i>iso</i> Propylacrylic acid	11	38.5
<i>iso</i> Valaraldehyde	<i>iso</i> Butylacrylic acid	10	40.4

Benzaldehyde was then condensed with malonic acid using the most suitable quantities (1 mol. of the aldehyde to 1 mol. of the base) of various organic bases as condensing agents. The results are summarised in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

Condensing agent.	Optimum temperature of the reaction.	Time taken for the reaction to complete.	Yield (%).
Quinoline	80°	6 hr.	80.0
<i>iso</i> Quinoline	65°	3½	91.4
Quinaldine	80°	8	23.8
α -Naphthoquinoline	80°	7	72.0
β - " "	90°	8	60.0
β benanthroline	65°	4	93.7
Acridine	100°	9	12.2
9-Methylacridine	97°	10	1.5
Pyridine	85°	5	76.1
α -Picoline	70°	2½	99.1
Lutidine	65°	2½	100.0
Collidine	90°	7	80.2
Piperidine	85°	6	90.0
Piperidine hydrochloride	122°	5	55.2
Dimethylaniline	85°	9	31.1
Diethylaniline	85°	8	25.2
Methylbenzylaniline	85°	10	30.2
Ethylbenzylaniline	85°	10	32.2

When no condensing agent was used, benzaldehyde condensed with malonic acid at 100° with formation of only benzylidene malonic acid, and the best yield that was obtained in course of ten experiments was 57.3 p. c. of the theoretical, by 6 hours heating. Not even the slightest trace of carbon dioxide was evolved at any time during these experiments. Raising the temperature of the reaction to even 130° did not produce any evolution of carbon dioxide or formation of cinnamic acid.